

VISCOSITY OF SOME COMPLEX SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 35°. PART II

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Viscosities of three tri-divalent complex salts, viz., hexamine-cobaltic sulphate, *tris*-ethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and *tris*-propylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate, have been measured. The Jones and Dole equation is found applicable in dilute solutions. The value of 'A' found and that derived with Falkenhagen and Vernon's equation (in parenthesis) are: 0.045 (0.0413), 0.0518 (0.0487), 0.0542 (0.0512). The ionic conductance of *tris*-propylenediamine ion at 35° is 83.10 ohm⁻¹.

In extension of the previous work (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 333) three complex tri-divalent salts that did not hydrolyse immediately were chosen for investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hexamine-cobaltic sulphate, *tris*-ethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and *tris*-propylenediamine cobaltic sulphate were prepared and purified by the method of Jenkins and Monk (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 68). Purity of the samples were tested by analysing for their Co, SO₄ and nitrogen contents. The first salt was carefully dried at 150°. A known weight of the salt was boiled for 3 hours with 2N sodium carbonate solution containing a little of caustic soda; the oxide formed was washed free from impurities, dissolved in H₂SO₄ and Co estimated gravimetrically with α -nitroso- β -naphthol (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", p. 547). The vacuum-dried samples of the other two salts were similarly analysed. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method and the sulphate was estimated gravimetrically (Vogel, *loc. cit.*, p. 547). The results for each of the three salts are shown below, the theoretically computed values are in parenthesis.

	% Co.	% N.	SO ₄ .
1. [Co(NH ₃) ₆] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	18.9 (19.3)	27.0 (25.45)	47.1 (47.04)
2. [Co(en) ₃] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	16.6 (17.58)	12.1 (10.2)	43.0 (42.98)
3. [Co(Pn) ₃] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	14.8 (15.62)	10.9 (9.15)	38.0 (38.2)

To ensure the purity of the samples equivalent conductances at three different concentrations of each of the three salts were measured at 25° and compared with the data of Jenkins and Monk (*loc. cit.*). There was good agreement between the two results, indicating that the salts were quite pure.

A stock solution of hexamine-cobaltic sulphate was prepared by weighing. The salt being slightly hygroscopic, the exact concentration of the stock solution was determined by estimating the sulphate. It was diluted to be exactly 0.0225 molar and this solution had a p_H of 6.0. From this solution other solutions were prepared by dilution. Stock solutions of *tris*-ethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and *tris*-propylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate were prepared and standardised as in case of the first salt.

The stock solutions of the latter two were 0.0070 and 0.0056 molar and had p_H 5.8 and 5.5 respectively. The stock solutions and the diluted solutions were never older than four days and during the period the p_H of the solutions did not change by more than 0.2 units.

In order to calculate the value of 'A' from Falkenhagen and Vernon's equation (*Physikal. Z.*, 1932, **33**, 140) the ionic conductance of $[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]^{3+}$ ion at 35° is necessary. For this purpose conductances were measured with an accuracy of 2 in 1000. The results are recorded in Table II. All other experimental procedures are similar to that shown in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$			$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$			$[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$		
$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.045\sqrt{c} + 0.35c$			$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.0518\sqrt{c} + 0.42c$			$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.0542\sqrt{c} + 0.45c$		
Conc.	η/η_0 exp.	η/η_0 calc.	Conc.	η/η_0 exp.	η/η_0 calc.	Conc.	η/η_0 exp.	η/η_0 calc.
0.0004	1.0009	1.0009	0.0004	1.0012	1.0012	0.0004	1.0012	1.0013
0.0006	1.0013	1.0013	0.0006	1.0015	1.0015	0.0006	1.0015	1.0016
0.0008	1.0016	1.0016	0.0008	1.0018	1.0018	0.0008	1.0019	1.0019
0.0009	1.0017	1.0017	0.0009	1.0019	1.0019	0.0009	1.0020	1.0020
0.0010	1.0018	1.0018	0.0010	1.0020	1.0021	0.0010	1.0021	1.0022
0.0011	1.0019	1.0019	0.0011	1.0021	1.0021	0.0011	1.0023	1.0023
0.0012	1.0020	1.0020	0.0012	1.0023	1.0023	0.0012	1.0024	1.0024
0.0013	1.0021	1.0021	0.0013	1.0024	1.0024	0.0013	1.0025	1.0026
0.0014	1.0022	1.0022	0.0014	1.0026	1.0025	0.0014	1.0027	1.0027
0.0015	1.0023	1.0023						

Concentration (c) is expressed in g. moles per litre.

TABLE II

Equiv. conc. $\times 10^4$	...	...	1.86	2.41	3.665	4.92	5.733
Δ	...	...	167.1	165.8	161.1	157.8	154.9
	$t^+ = 81.3$						

The experimental values of 'A' and 'B' for the electrolytes were obtained by plotting $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{c}$ against $\sqrt{c}$. This ionic conductance of the $[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]^{3+}$ was calculated from the observed data with a knowledge of the ionic conductance of the sulphate ion at 25° (Harned and Owen "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solution", p. 172) and its temperature coefficient.

The calculated and the experimental values of 'A' and the experimental values of 'B' for various salts are shown below.

TABLE III

Salt	'A' exp.	'A' calc.	'B'
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	0.043	0.0413	0.35
$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	0.0518	0.0487	0.42
$[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	0.0542	0.0512	0.45

The experimental values of 'A' for the salts examined are higher than the theoretical value, although they are of the same order. It is of interest to note that in the case of *tris*-ethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and *tris*-propylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate, the difference between the experimental and the theoretical value of 'A' is almost equal *i. e.*, 0.0031 and 0.0030 and the values of 'B' are also nearly the same, 0.42 and 0.45 respectively. With this meagre data no general conclusion can be drawn, but it can be stated that the factors that are responsible for the constant difference between the experimental and the theoretical values of 'A' are influencing the two salts to the same extent. The very near values of 'B' also indicate the same.

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